

The impact of supplier partnerships on quality of information sharing, commitment, trust and supply chain performance in the automotive industry

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The South African automotive industry is continually under threat of not achieving sustainable supply chain performance. Factors negatively affecting this industry include the low quality of the information shared, inadequate commitment and trust among supply chain participants, and the country's poor economic performance. The purpose of this study is to analyze the relationship between supplier partnership, quality, information sharing, commitment, trust, and supply chain performance in the South African automotive industry. Data analysis techniques include descriptive and inferential statistics. The results of the research study show positive relationships between the study variables, namely, supplier partnership, quality of information sharing, commitment, trust, and supply chain performance. The quality of information shared among the supplier partners has the most significant impact on the commitment. This suggests that continuous improvement of information quality can lead to better synchronization of supply and demand in the automotive supply chain.

Keywords: Buyer-supplier, trust, quality of information sharing, supplier partnership commitment, supply chain performance

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Introduction

Supplier partnership plays a key role in identifying competitive priorities, such as offering quality products and the ability to respond to changing customer demands. According to Jajja, Asif, Montabon and Chatha (2019), supplier partnership is defined as monitoring collaborations that communicate information to increase the firms' supply chain effectiveness by integrating committed and trustworthy supply chain partners. In other words, the quality of information shared in the supplier partnership is important. According to Dwaikat, Money, Behasthi, and Salehi-Sangari (2018), this occurs because the foundation of

any supplier relationship is built on the quality of information shared to achieve effective customer satisfaction and increased performance. However, the sharing of accurate and useful information results from commitment and trust in the supply chain. Trust plays an essential role in supply chain performance. It is based on the partner's willingness to handle conflicts in the firm and the ability to show great adaptation to the daily operations of the firm (Reiersen 2019). Therefore, achieving supply chain performance is based on the level of trust and commitment between strategic alliances in the automotive industry. Supply chain performance is a key metric that plays a crucial role in the overall effectiveness of a supply chain (Ikome, Laseinde & Katumba 2022, Mani, Gunasekaran & Delgado 2017). Therefore, firms need to improve the efficiency of their supply chain performance to maintain competitiveness. The purpose of this study is to discuss the basic principles of improving uncertainty in supplier collaborations through the communication of quality information, which enhances supplier commitment and trust, ultimately leading the firm to achieve a competitive advantage through improved operational performance.

The South African automotive industry is continuously under the endangerment of various elements, such as the deterioration of quality information sharing and the acknowledgment of insufficient trust and commitment among supply chain partners, which can lead to inefficient and ineffective supply chain performance (Rathilall & Singh 2018, Reddy et al. 2016). These elements have an impact on the reduction of production power in various industries. Therefore, automotive dealerships need to communicate real-time information about market conditions and customer demands to capitalize on supply chain efficiencies. Globally, the automotive industry has faced challenges, such as supplier alliances that fail to strengthen buyer-supplier relationships, the intensification of quality information that is shared, and a lack of commitment and trust in the supply chain (Myrelid & Jonsson 2019). Further, as competition intensifies, the commitment to manage effective supply chain collaboration among automobile industries also becomes challenging. This may be due to the growing development of supply chain partnerships that can meet high-order demand and multiple loops, utilizing information technology with feedback structures among supply chain partners to ensure improved operational performance (Zondo 2018).

Our study aims to determine the extent to which supplier partnerships in the automotive industry influence the quality of the information shared. This study further investigates the extent to which information quality determines the level of commitment and trust, as well as its influence on supply chain performance (Meyer-Weitz, Baasner-Weitz & Weitz 2015). The concept of achieving supply chain performance efficiencies through various elements in the automotive industry has been researched on local and international scales (Sternbeck & Kuhn 2013). However, none of the previous studies tested the same conceptual framework presented in this study in the South African automotive industry. Therefore, this study seeks to fill the research gap and establish the links between the study variables.

Commitment-Trust Theory

Theories are systematic sets of interrelated statements and constructs designed to explain certain aspects of social life (Wang, Wang & Liu 2016). They further explain that a theory is a well-structured conceptual framework that provides an early understanding and explanation of the nature and dynamics of issues, problems, and phenomena. We draw on commitment-trust theory as its theoretical foundation. The theory encompasses and facilitates the development of complex relationships characterized by a willingness to trust others in achieving effective and efficient operational performance (Morgan & Hunt 1994). Traditionally, this theory examines the stronghold of supplier collaborations that are driven by shared commitment based on trust. The strength of supplier alliances characterizes the success of committed and trustworthy supply chain collaboration. With this, business performance in terms of expansion and customer satisfaction is ensured (Dwaikat, Money, Behasthi & Salehi-Sangari 2018). Primarily, the theory explores the development and growth of long-term supply chain partners who are

not power conscious but who are committed and trustworthy to ensure firms can deliver efficient operational performance (Wang, Wang & Liu 2016). The theory plays a significant role, driven by supply chain partners, which enhances a positive outcome throughout the lifecycle of the relationship (South African Government 2018). Although supplier readiness plays a crucial role in the automotive industry, commitment trust theory is employed to monitor systems and components that evaluate suppliers' ability to produce and deliver the required product in the right quality and quantities, ensuring effective and efficient supply chain performance (Wang et al. 2016).

The South African automotive industry constantly faces changing market demand. As such, suppliers can communicate real-time information to positively affect supplier knowledge and experience in production and product development (South African Government 2018). This theory suggests that effective supplier collaboration is achievable through mutual commitment and trust in sharing quality information. Commitment and trust are crucial factors for the success of cooperative relationships between supply chain partners. As such, a long-term, mutually beneficial collaboration that ensures customer satisfaction can result. Commitment is likely to arise in the absence of prior experience of trust between supply chain partners. However, trust is the principal antecedent of commitment because it ensures that the quality of information shared among supply chain partners is accurate and reliable (Wang et al. 2016). Therefore, to achieve successful partnerships, collaborations should be based on commitment and trust between individual firms in the automotive industry. Cooperative partnerships are highly influenced by inter-organizational commitment, which aims to sustain partnerships for the long run. Figure 1 shows the hypothesized relationship among variables used in this study.

Hypotheses Development

Figure 1. Conceptual Diagram

Source: the author

Supplier Partnership, Quality of Information Sharing

Previous studies have noted that supplier partnerships are influenced by the quality of information shared between supply chain partners (Arrfou 2019, Dwaikat et al. 2018, Mani et al. 2017). The South African automotive industry can establish a competitive position through strategic supplier partnerships, leveraging the skills to communicate quality information in real-time, which enables effective and efficient customer satisfaction (Zelbst et al. 2014). For example, long-term supplier partnerships work together to share resources and communicate daily operational quality information, thereby achieving the core value of the automotive industry in delivering high-quality products to the market (South African Government 2018, Uca et al. 2017). Supplier partnerships play a crucial role in driving new product innovation,

facilitated by the delivery of high-quality information and the identification of challenges posed by changing customer demands in the automotive industry. According to Arrfou (2019), supplier partnerships offer an opportunity for a successful flow of information that can enhance the firm's operational performance and improve its competitive advantage in the industry. Therefore, the automotive industry will be unable to achieve a competitive advantage without strategic supplier collaborations that communicate real-time information on market demand. As a result, the supplier partnership enables firms to share quality information with their supply chain partners, thereby maximizing the firm's competitive position and improving supply chain performance. This study, therefore, proposes that:

H1. Supplier partnerships have a positive influence on the quality of information exchange.

Quality of Information Sharing, Commitment, and Trust

Information sharing is highly characterized by the value of information shared both upstream and downstream in the supply chain (Martins et al. 2017). The South African automotive industry can achieve a competitive position through strategic communication of quality information that improves efficient and effective supply chain flow. For example, a lack of commitment and trust among supplier alliances can result in insufficient communication of quality information, which directly impacts a firm's day-to-day operations, creating challenges in meeting customer demands (Najjar Dahabiyeh & Nawayseh 2019). Therefore, adequate communication of quality information, shared through the guidance of commitment and trust, will enable firms to meet customer order demands with minimal hindrance to their operations, resulting in increased operational efficiency and performance. The existing literature suggests that information sharing fosters commitment and trust among suppliers, which in turn influences opportunities for growth and customer satisfaction (Arrfou 2019). As a result, successful supply chain performance can be achieved through the integration of supplier alliances, which facilitate the communication of information, foster complete trust, and promote commitment in the supply chain network (Marinagi et al. 2015). The quality of information sharing mediates the effective flow of knowledge sharing among supply chain partners, which can enforce a competitive environment in the automotive industry (Abdulla et al. 2014). Therefore, quality information cannot be achieved without the relationships of commitment and trust between supply chain partners. This study, therefore, proposes that:

H2. The quality of information sharing has a positive influence on commitment.

Information Sharing and Trust

The existing literature suggests that information sharing fosters trust, which in turn influences opportunities for growth and customer satisfaction (Abdulla et al. 2014, Arrfou 2019). There is a significant relationship between the quality of information and trust. An improvement in the level of information quality may motivate supply chain partners to increase their willingness and openness to sharing information, which in turn may strengthen the relationship and enhance trust among them. Previous scholars, such as Nyaga, Whipple, and Lynch (2010), acknowledge the significance of the relationship by stipulating that information sharing is vital to the trust-building process, as it enables each organization to understand the other's routines and establish conflict resolution mechanisms. Further, Mofokeng and Chinomona (2019) stipulate that when supply chain partners frequently share vital and high-quality information, trust can be automatically established. Given the stated results, it can be concluded that the quality of information may strongly improve the level of trust in the automotive industry. Therefore, quality information cannot be achieved without trust between supply chain partners. This study, therefore, proposes that:

H3. The quality of information sharing has a positive influence on trust.

Commitment, Trust, and Supply Chain Performance

Trust enables firms to be more competitive by improving supply chain performance, reducing operational costs, and achieving successful supply chain collaborations (Fantazy & Mukerji 2021). The South African automotive industry can achieve a competitive position through the influence of trust, which communicates the willingness of suppliers to take risks to improve organizational performance (Hudnurkar, Jakhar & Rathod 2014). As a result, trust leads to an increase in supply chain partnerships, which subsequently yields a competitive advantage while positively impacting the firms' supply chain performance (Najjar et al. 2019). Therefore, the positive contribution of supplier partnership through trust will influence the effect of collaborative advantage on firm supply chain performance. Trust optimizes resources in the supply chain, thereby minimizing the risk of not meeting customer requirements (Wahyudi 2014). Supplier partnerships provide an opportunity for improvement that will enhance the firm's overall supply chain performance. Therefore, trust is considered a positive outcome in the supply chain, which facilitates the flow of information through strategic partners, thereby enhancing the supplier's commitment and trust, enabling them to compete successfully and achieve effective performance. Researchers have revealed that the automotive industry cannot compete successfully without the influence of trust among supply chain partners (Lavassani & Movahedi 2018, Pakura et al. 2019). In conclusion, trust maximizes the effectiveness of supplier partnerships by fostering commitment and trust to share real-time information, which is crucial for achieving a competitive advantage and optimal supply chain performance (Reiersen 2019). Therefore, this study proposes the following:

H4. Commitment has a positive influence on supply chain performance.

Trust and Supply Chain Performance

Trust leads to an increase in supply chain partnerships, which subsequently results in a competitive advantage while positively affecting a firm's supply chain performance (Abdulla & Musa 2014). Therefore, the positive contribution of supplier partnership through trust will influence the effect of collaborative advantage on the firm's supply chain performance (Smith et al. 2014). Trust is considered a positive outcome in the supply chain, which facilitates the flow of information through strategic partners, thereby enhancing supplier commitment and trust and enabling them to compete successfully and attain effective performance (Lavassani & Movahedi, 2018). In conclusion, trust maximizes the effectiveness of supplier partnerships by fostering commitment and trust to share real-time information, which is crucial for achieving a competitive advantage and optimal supply chain performance (Reiersen 2019). This study, therefore, proposes that:

H5. Trust has a positive influence on supply chain performance.

Methodology

The target population for the study is personnel working in the automotive industry supply chain in South Africa. It consists of vehicle salespeople, spare part distributors, supply chain and quality managers, engineering change specialists, logistics planners, material controllers, quality specialists, production line operators, and material receivers in Gauteng and Eastern Cape Provinces. A historical sampling approach was employed in this research study to determine the sample size (Mani et al. 2017, Smith et al. 2014). In this research study, a sample size of 200 respondents was secured. A non-probability convenience sampling method was used because it is inexpensive, provides a quick estimate of the truth, and is accessible to respondents. Structured self-administered questionnaires were employed to gather data from respondents, enhancing ease of coding, analysis, and interpretation of responses while minimizing non-responses. We solicited demographic information from respondents, such as gender, age, ethnicity,

language, and educational level. The variables were operationalized by borrowing scales from Li et al. (2006) for *supplier relationship*, from Wiengarten et al. (2010) for *information sharing quality*, from Smith et al. (2014) for *commitment*, from Kwon and Suh (2005) for *trust*, and from Mani et al. (2017) for *supply chain performance*. All questionnaire components utilized a five-point Likert scale, known for its respondent-friendly nature and ease of construction (DeVellis 2012). Following several follow-ups, 127 questionnaires were used out of the 200 distributed, resulting in a 64% response rate and mitigating the non-response bias risk. To further address non-response bias, the questionnaire targeted a diverse demographic encompassing various departments, roles, and SME backgrounds, ensuring comprehensive representation of the automotive supply chain workforce and reducing biases associated with underrepresentation.

Sample Characteristics

About 61% of the respondents are men and 39% are women. Nieman and Nieuwenhuizen (2009) report that there are few women in the automotive industry because the automotive industry is often perceived as an industry for men, as they are considered to have more knowledge regarding automobiles. In terms of age groups, approximately 17% were aged between 18 and 25, 35% were aged between 26 and 35, 32% were aged between 36 and 45, 11% were aged between 46 and 55, and 5% were aged 56 and older. Most graduates enter the job market as interns, where they rotate in different departments to gain working experience. By this, the age group of 26-35 is either in internships or learnerships, thus roaming between various departments. Approximately 16% have obtained a Matriculation, 17% have received a Certificate, 40% hold a Diploma, 20% have a Degree, 6% hold a higher degree, and 1% of the participants are holders of Master's or PhD qualifications. This indicates that most employees in the automotive industry are qualified individuals, and they need to possess these qualifications due to the processes and procedures that ensure every product distributed to customers is of high quality, thereby protecting their safety.

Analysis and Results

The data were then captured in a Microsoft Excel spreadsheet. The Excel spreadsheet containing the captured data was also reviewed and cleaned to identify and correct any missing entries. This was followed by importing the data into the Smart Partial Least Squares (Smart-PLS 3) structural equation modeling, a variance-based. Once the data were formatted, the next step was to use descriptive statistics to analyze the demographic profile of the respondents. As indicated in Table 1, the intercorrelation values for all paired latent variables are less than 1.0 and, therefore, indicate that a discriminant validity does exist (De Vries, Walter, Van Der Vegt & Essens 2014).

Table 1. Correlation among Variables

Variables	Commitment	CIS	SP	SCP	Trust
Commitment	.86				
Quality of Information Sharing (CIS)	.70	.81			
Supplier Partnerships (SP)	.64	.67	.83		
Supply chain performance (SCP)	.63	.48	.47	.89	
Trust	.59	.48	.53	.60	.84

Sources: the authors

Cronbach's Alpha and inter-item correlation values were used to validate the internal consistency of the constructs. Both values range from .7 to .9, indicating that items fit together conceptually (Tapsir, Pa & Zamri 2018). The results also indicate that all composite reliability (CR) values (.92 to .96) exceeded the threshold of .7 as recommended by (Tsai & Huang 2007). The average variance extracted (AVE) measures

range from .66 to .80, which is above .50 (Alwi, Bakar & Talib 2012). All the measurement factor loadings are acceptable for this research because they are greater than .5, as suggested by Van der Vaart (2021). Figure 1 and Table 2 present the five hypothesized relationships, the path coefficients, and p-values.

Table 2 Results of Hypotheses Testing

Path Relationship	Hypotheses	Co-efficient	<i>p</i>	Outcome
Partnership → Information Sharing	<i>H1</i> (+)	.67	.00	Supported
Information Sharing → Commitment	<i>H2</i> (+)	.70	.00	Supported
Information Sharing → Trust	<i>H3</i> (+)	.48	.00	Supported
Commitment → Supply Chain Performance	<i>H4</i> (+)	.42	.00	Supported
Trust → Supply Chain Performance	<i>H5</i> (+)	.35	.00	Supported

Sources: the authors

Discussion

The Commitment-Trust Theory posits that robust partnerships are founded on mutual objectives, transparency, and dependable communication (Morgan & Hunt 1994). In examining *H1*, the study demonstrates that supplier partnerships ($\beta=.67, p<.00$) considerably enhance the quality of information, supporting the theory's focus on open communication as a cornerstone of trust. This finding aligns with previous studies (Dwaikat et al. 2018, Jajja et al. 2019), which suggest that strong collaborations with suppliers facilitate the exchange of real-time, accurate, and valuable information. Without established and effective supplier partnerships, most attempts to manage the flow of information or materials across supply chains tend to be inadequate. Therefore, efficient supplier partnerships are founded on increased information sharing, yielding benefits such as decreased total costs and reduced inventory levels. Collaborative supplier relationships in emerging markets are essential for minimizing supply chain disruptions (Fekpe & Fiagbey 2021). Given the challenges facing South Africa's automotive industry, including economic instability, supply chain disruptions, and variable demand, automotive companies must solidify their supplier alliances to enhance information exchange.

The theory posits that trust is a precursor to commitment, suggesting that when partners share accurate information, they perceive each other as reliable, which in turn leads to long-term dedication (Morgan & Hunt 1994). *H2* revealed the strongest relationship ($\beta=.70, p<.00$) was between information quality and commitment, indicating that when suppliers receive reliable data, they are more likely to remain committed to long-term partnerships. From the South African automotive context, many local suppliers struggle with inconsistent demand forecasts and production delays due to poor information sharing (Reddy 2016, Rathilall & Singh 2018). Based on the results presented in Table 2, it can be inferred that information quality is crucial for fostering commitment among all participants in the automotive industry's supply chain. This is supported by Fekpe and Fiagbey (2021), who argue that information transparency is a key driver of trust in African supply chains.

Consequently, the findings of *H3* confirm that trust ($\beta=.48, p<.00$) is reinforced when information is accurate and timely, supporting prior research (Mofokeng & Chinomona 2019) that stipulates that when supply chain partners share vital and high-quality information frequently, trust can be established. The South African automotive industry faces trust deficits due to historical issues, including late payments, order cancellations, and unreliable lead times (Zondo 2018). This study suggests that information sharing is vital to the trust-building process, as it enables each organization to understand the other's routines and establish effective conflict resolution mechanisms. Given the results stated, it can be concluded that the quality of information may strongly improve the level of trust in the automotive industry.

The theory posits that commitment and trust reduce transaction costs and enhance performance (Morgan & Hunt 1994). In *H4*, the study found that commitment ($\beta=.42, p<.00$) directly improves supply chain performance, confirming Morgan & Hunt's (1994) Commitment-Trust Theory. In the South African

automotive sector, the rising competition from imported vehicles means that local manufacturers need dedicated suppliers to maintain cost efficiency and product quality. In doing so, a buyer-supplier long-term commitment is a key driver of supply chain longevity and performance. This is supported by Fantasy and Mukerji (2021), who state that long-term supplier commitment is vital for cost efficiency in volatile economies.

Finally, *H5* also indicated a significant positive correlation between trust and the performance of supply chains ($\beta=.35, p<.00$), potentially decreasing conflicts between automotive buyers and suppliers, as well as operational risks. In the context of the South African automotive industry, trust is crucial in mitigating risks such as supplier failures, raw material shortages, and labor strikes (Ikome et al. 2022). This suggests that prioritizing trust in South Africa's automotive sectors will likely lead to better performance in their supply chains. Fantasy and Mukerji (2021), emphasizes that trust is crucial for establishing strong and enduring relationships among supply chain participants, thereby enhancing overall supply chain performance, even in volatile economies. This insight suggests that the South African automotive industry needs to engage in supplier development initiatives, boosting transparency and joint risk management to enhance dependability.

Implication for Managers

The study has numerous valuable implications. Theoretically, it contributes to the existing body of knowledge by confirming the Commitment-Trust Theory in a developing economy like South Africa, which faces unique challenges such as infrastructure gaps and economic instability. It extends the theory by proving that Information quality is a critical mediator in addition to trust and commitment. It also serves as a basis for understanding research methodologies in the literature on supply chain management. Further, the paper offers a detailed conceptualization of how supplier partnerships, information sharing quality, commitment, trust, and supply chain performance interrelate in the South African automotive industry.

Practically, the study offers valuable insights for supply chain collaborators in South Africa's automotive sector, focusing on strategies to enhance supply chain performance. Automotive giants such as Toyota South Africa, BMW SA, and Volkswagen SA are encouraged to adopt digital solutions, including ERP systems and blockchain, to promote transparency and enhance communication effectiveness with suppliers, thereby minimizing delays and miscommunication. To improve the quality of shared information, introducing collaborative planning, forecasting, and replenishment (CPFR) systems is recommended to synchronize supplier commitments with market needs, minimizing stock shortages and overproduction. To bolster trust among partners, automakers should consider employing performance-based contracts and joint problem-solving strategies to foster a trustworthy environment, ensuring suppliers feel valued and secure in sustained partnerships. Implementing reward schemes for long-standing supplier commitments could further support production and logistics stability.

Limitations

All studies have certain limitations, and this study is no exception. The study has offered new knowledge. However, despite the relevance of the knowledge obtained, it is essential to note that the investigation has limitations. Several elements may have negatively affected the results. One of the elements is related to the scope of the study. The study's limited scope to one province, Gauteng, can be viewed as a disadvantage, as assessing the performance of a supply chain typically requires a broader geographic scope. A substantial expansion of the scope to at least two provinces would yield a more reliable results. Further, the lack of monitoring during the completion process of the questionnaires is also a limitation. It would be fitting for the researcher to guide the respondents through the questions presented, providing them with a holistic understanding of the sentences and obtaining honest feedback from the

respondents. One of the best alternatives is to adopt a mixed-methods approach, in which respondents can be interviewed, which can be time-consuming but still provides more reliable results than responding to an extensive questionnaire.

Future Research Directions

This research investigated the impact of supplier partnerships on the quality of information sharing, commitment, trust, and overall supply chain performance in South Africa's automotive sector. While this study highlighted some aspects, additional issues remain underexplored and present opportunities for future investigation. Specifically, the supply chain performance in the automotive domain involves both theoretical insights and practical implementations. Therefore, emphasis should be placed on effectively managing supply chain partners directly involved in the automotive industry. Future literature could explore a range of operational and strategic solutions addressing contemporary challenges in the automotive sector, with a particular focus on significant supply chain management issues. This study could also be extended to encompass vital sectors of the South African automotive industry, including operations, transportation, finance, manufacturing, and production, thereby facilitating a comparative analysis. Additionally, future investigations might analyze supply chain constraints such as delayed deliveries, extended payment terms, and variations in goods quality and quantity, as these factors could impede sustainable supply chain success in South Africa's automotive industry. Employing a mixed-methods approach could also yield comprehensive data that extends beyond the scope of this study. Future inquiries explore the correlation between supplier partnership and supply chain performance, assess the link between information-sharing quality and supply chain efficiency, and investigate the interplay between commitment and trust.

Conclusion

The research provides a detailed conceptual framework for understanding the dynamics between supplier partnerships, the quality of information exchange, commitment, trust, and the performance of supply chains in South Africa's automotive sector, an area with limited research. The study provides valuable insights for supply chain stakeholders in South Africa's automotive industry to enhance their supply chain effectiveness. It affirms that partnerships with suppliers, high-quality information, commitment, and trust are interconnected elements that drive supply chain performance in this sector. Considering automotive industry challenges, such as economic strain, global competition, and inefficiencies in supply chains, South African automakers are advised to improve digital integration such as IoT and AI-driven demand forecasting to enhance information exchange; implement trust-building measures like joint training and fair contract agreements; and strengthen long-term supplier commitments through incentives and collaborative planning. By doing so, the South African automotive industry can enhance its resilience, reduce costs, and maintain competitiveness in an unpredictable market.

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